

**ISSUES OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE AND SPIRITUALITY IN THE
AVESTO WRITTEN MONUMENT**

Seytmuratov Kalbay - candidate of pedagogical sciences, associate professor
Nukus Pedagogical Institute named after Ajiniyaz, Uzbekistan

Abstract *The article deals with ecological culture and the ideas of environmental spirituality set forth in the Avesto written monument, the relevance of their use in the field of modern continuing education.*

Keywords: *"Avesto", ecology, ecological culture, ecological spirituality, nature conservation, lifelong education, youth education, people's health.*

**"ISSUES OF ECOLOGICAL CULTURE AND SPIRITUALITY IN THE
WRITTEN MONUMENT "AVESTO"**

***Seytmuratov Kalbay - Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor
Nukus Pedagogical Institute named after Azhiniyaz, Uzbekistan***

ANNOTATION

The article deals with ecological culture and the ideas of ecological spirituality set forth in the written monument "Avesto", the relevance of their use in the field of modern continuing education.

Keywords: "Avesto", ecology, ecological culture, ecological spirituality, nature conservation, continuing education, youth education, people's health.

The first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A.Karimov, in his speech at the opening ceremony of the memorial complex built to commemorate the 2700th anniversary of the book "Avesta", said: "considering the ideas and thoughts contained in the book "Avesta", one can only be amazed at how deep their meanings are, this unique work describes the attitude to nature, the integrity of the universe, harmony between man and nature, it is indicated and justified that the protection and protection of the environment are the main task of man [1:4]. Consequently, the development of ecological culture and spirituality of the people, especially the youth, is one of the urgent tasks of today. "Avesta" is a sacred book of Zoroastrianism, it was created at the end of the VII-beginning of the XVI century BC, the form of the book acquired in the first century BC. According to the historian Tabari, this book is written with a golden pen on parchment made of 12 thousand bull skins. The extant copy of the book was copied in 1324 and is kept in the library of the city of Copenhagen. "Avesto" is not only a religious book, it is also considered a monument with social, philosophical, pedagogical, cultural, literary, historical values. The main teaching of the Avesta is built around a troika aimed at the comprehensive development of a person: "good thoughts (humata), a good word (huhta), a good deed (huvarshta)." In the book "Avesto", along with the improvement of nature, the main place is also occupied by elements of ecological culture and spirituality.

The essence of the term "Ecological culture" means the concept of a deep understanding of the laws of the development of nature and its use in the long and

short term, taking into account the consequences of human actions. Ecological culture is considered to be one part of universal culture, which is the fruit of the material and spiritual environment. Environmental education is the result of the process and the process of deep assimilation of the knowledge necessary for the scientifically based implementation of measures for the protection of nature. Ecological education is understood as the process of constantly increasing the level of spiritual attitude to nature by influencing human consciousness, thinking, and worldview.

Spirituality includes the concepts of culture, enlightenment and ideology. Since spirituality appears together with language, reason and the ability to think before a person becomes literate, civilized. Spirituality begins to be established as the title and level of humanity of his Majesty the man. [2:269]

In the Zoroastrian teaching, the meaning of life for a person is honesty and purity. And it is also said that "you need to think more about the soul than about the body, if your spiritual world is clean and transparent, your material well-being will grow" [2:264].

In the Zoroastrian culture, nature protection and environmental cleanliness were considered the main tasks. Therefore, the cleaning of the environment from garbage, the processing of clothing and food by different methods was promoted. At the same time, burning, cold and heat were used, as well as chemical methods: various herbs were burned (onion, garlic, aloe, harmala (adraspan)). The improvement of conditions for grazing and breeding of domestic animals was promoted, not to torture animals, not to cause their untimely death, to destroy sick animals and insects. The Avesta says that the main cause of the origin of the vast majority of diseases are excessive heat, cold, hunger, overeating, eating spoiled

food, depression, not keeping clean. It is strictly required to keep clean and timely cutting of hair and nails, hair and nails should be buried deep so that dogs, cats and birds cannot open in places where no one will see them. It was considered a sin to spit in the water, comb your hair near the fire. The rules of personal hygiene, the need for body care are described, the need for hygienic education of young people is emphasized, as well as the use of punishment for those who do not comply with hygiene rules. This book says that a book, earth, water, tree, etc. also have a soul. There is a notion that through this moving soul the sun gives warmth, water flows, plants grow, a person develops, his morality is formed. [3:71].

The famous German philosopher Hegel characterizes the Zoroastrian doctrine "as a religion of substance or nature, which is in transition to a religion of freedom" - [3:70]. Our first president, I.A. Karimov, in his interview given to a reporter of the Turkestan newspaper, says: "Avesto is a book that not only a person is sacred, a handful of earth, a sip of water, a sip of air are also sacred." He called this book "the Guidebook of life" (AET juries) . [2:259]

In conclusion, we can say that the thoughts expressed in the book "Avesto", aimed at protecting nature, at a reasonable attitude to the plant and animal world, at the formation of a culture of positive attitude to the environment, and today do not lose their significance. Since the ecological process is carried out in an assembled form, it requires innovative thinking, worldview, moral, cultural and spiritual maturity. Therefore, we must try to further increase the level of environmental education, environmental culture and spirituality, especially among young people.

LIST of LITERATURE

1. Journal "Uzbek language and Literature" No. 6, 2001 - 3-7c,

2. Otaboev, Sh. "Problems of culture and spirituality in ecology"/Sh.Otaboev, S.Mirvaliev, E.Tursunov, -Tashkent, Nishon Noshir, 2009, - 280s
3. Aleutov, U. Formation and development of educational thoughts in Karakalpakstan - Nukus, Bilim-1993 - 503 s.